

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文集结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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企业智力潜力的概念：定义、经济本质与结构

**THE CONCEPT OF INTELLECTUAL POTENTIAL OF AN
ENTERPRISE: DEFINITION, ECONOMIC ESSENCE AND
STRUCTURE**

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注解。在现代条件下，企业结构产生新知识、有效利用和传播新知识的能力，以及创造突破性信息技术及其在创新产品生产中的应用的的能力，在很大程度上决定了国民经济的竞争力，并成为国民经济的基础。 确保各国社会经济可持续发展。 对此，国民经济改革的主要目标应是向知识产品生产转型，利用企业智力资源，提高高新技术产业在GDP结构中的比重。 为此，首先要加大力度为企业智力创新能力的发展及其在生产活动中的实际运用创造有利条件。 这就是为什么智力潜力的形成和开发、智力资源的集约化利用问题对于工业企业来说比以往任何时候都更加重要。

关键词：企业、人员、智力潜力、智力资源、结构、经济本质。

Annotation. *In modern conditions, the ability of business structures to generate new knowledge, its effective use and dissemination, as well as to create breakthrough information technologies and their application in the production of innovative products largely determine the competitiveness of the national economy and become the basis for ensuring sustainable socio-economic development of each country. In this regard, the main goal of reforming national economies should be the transition to the production of intellectual products and increasing the share of high-tech industries in the structure of GDP through the use of intellectual resources of enterprises. To achieve it, it is necessary, first of all, to intensify the creation of favorable conditions for the development of intellectual and innovative capabilities of enterprises and their practical application in production activities. That is why the issues of formation and development of intellectual potential, intensification of the use of intellectual resources are more relevant than ever for industrial enterprises.*

Keywords: *enterprise, personnel, intellectual potential, intellectual resources, structure, economic essence.*

Introduction.

The introduction of modern information technologies into all areas of production and other economic activities has contributed to a fundamental change in the nature of human labor, gradually replacing heavy physical labor with intellectual labor of operators of technological lines and production processes. Intellectual work stimulates enterprise personnel to self-realization, improving their managerial and professional competencies, increasing the amount of knowledge, learning new skills and work techniques in accordance with new qualification requirements. Therefore, in the development of the intellectualization of labor, the organization of training within systems of continuous professional development and retraining of specialists at enterprises, which allow maintaining the required level of knowledge and quality of professional activity of their personnel, depending on their individual and acquired abilities, becomes important.

The essence of the intellectualization of labor lies in the generation of new knowledge, ideas, hypotheses, which are subsequently transformed into the development of innovations and modern information technologies. Thus, enterprise personnel become specialists in intellectual work and possessors not only of new knowledge and information, but also one of the defining resources of the knowledge-based information economy. In other words, intellectual labor specialists form the intellectual potential of modern enterprises.

The concept of the intellectual potential of an enterprise is quite difficult to unambiguously define, since it includes a wide range of other concepts, such as generating new knowledge, increasing managerial and professional competencies, developing staff's abilities for self-realization through the continuous improvement of their skills and abilities. At the same time, the entire set of these and other concepts undergoes dynamic changes over time under the influence of a large number of multidirectional factors. In this study, the authors will clarify the definition of the concept of intellectual capital; reveal its economic essence and the structure of its components.

Purpose of the study.

The purpose of this study is to clarify the definition of the concept of intellectual capital in relation to the objective realities of the modern economy, to reveal its economic essence and the structure of its components based on an analysis of the works of foreign and modern Russian researchers, as well as taking into account the peculiarities of the organization of practical production activities of enterprises that contribute to increasing their competitiveness.

Materials and methods.

In the scientific works of many modern economists, more and more attention is paid to research into such a concept as the “intellectual potential” of an enterprise. However, in relation to the practical activities of enterprises themselves, a clear definition of this concept has not yet been formulated. Most existing works reveal only individual components of this concept, which correlate with specific conditions and types of production activities of enterprises. A systematic approach to revealing the economic essence of the concept of “intellectual potential” of an enterprise and its structure was used in a small number of studies, which were of a rather fragmentary nature. Meanwhile, almost all domestic researchers have come to understand that in modern conditions, the development of an enterprise’s intellectual capital ensures an increase in its competitiveness and an increase in the efficiency of production activities. Ultimately, through the effective use of all components of their intellectual capital, enterprises can significantly reduce the negative impact of sanctions restrictions, which hinder their progressive development.

The main methods used in this work will be a comprehensive analysis of modern research and the approaches used in them to reveal the economic essence of the concept of “intellectual potential” of enterprises and its structure, as well as identifying the practical features of its application to improve the efficiency of their production activities.

Literature review.

The basis for the theoretical justification of existing approaches to determining the economic essence and structural components of intellectual potential was formed by the works of J. Galbraith, T. Stewart, E. Toffler, B. Lev and other famous scientists.

The concept of intellectual potential was first introduced into economics by the famous American economist J. Galbraith in 1969. Initially, he defined its meaning as a product of “intellectual activity” or intellectual property consisting of patents, copyrights, trademarks, and know-how and other forms [1]. Then many scientists began to consider intellectual potential as a combination of intellectual property and knowledge of enterprise personnel. Thus, T. Stewart believed that intellectual potential is the totality of knowledge of all personnel of an enterprise, which ensures its competitiveness. At the same time, he did not take into account the organizational features of the practice of managing this knowledge and the dynamics of their change over time [2]. Some founders of the theory of intellectual potential identified it with the intellectual potential of the enterprise’s personnel, considering it as a determining resource that contributes to the growth of competitiveness based on the use of new knowledge and modern technologies for organizing production [3]. Close enough to this approach is the definition of intellectual potential

made by B. Lev, who defined this concept as “an immaterial source of future benefits generated by innovation, unique technologies for organizing production and managing human resources” [4].

At the beginning of our research, it seems necessary to dwell on the content of the concept of intellectual potential. In accordance with the definition of Gavrilova M.A. and Shepelev V.M., potential can be considered as a space of probabilistically determined possible states of an enterprise as an economic entity carrying out its production activities in specific conditions. Probabilistically determined possible states depend not only on environmental factors, but on the control actions of the enterprise management, which influence the redistribution of the weights of its probabilistic states through the effective use of existing and the formation of new conditions for the production activity of the enterprise [5]. Based on this definition, the intellectual potential of an enterprise should be understood as the totality of the abilities of its personnel to generate new knowledge, their systematization and further transformation into information resources and technologies necessary for successful production activity of the enterprise.

The intellectual potential of an enterprise can be considered as its existing stock of knowledge, information technologies and other types of intellectual resources that can be realized through its structural components to increase competitiveness and generate additional income for the owners of the enterprise.

At the same time, the intellectual resources of an enterprise are determined by the totality of knowledge, professional skills, and intellectual abilities of its personnel, on the basis of which innovative products are created [6]. Thus, the intellectual potential of an enterprise is determined by the processes of generating new knowledge and other information resources, the availability and effective use of modern information management and production technologies, as well as other components.

Results and discussion.

Based on the research and analysis of existing approaches to the concept of intellectual capital of an enterprise in relation to modern realities, it should be understood as a set of structural components (personnel, social and organizational capital), which is in continuous development based on increasing managerial and professional competencies, expanding the practice of using modern information technologies and the constant generation of new knowledge.

From this definition follows the economic essence and intellectual potential of the enterprise, which can be represented through the totality of the intellectual abilities of the enterprise personnel, which include professional qualification level, the required amount of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, as well as experience in intellectual work. They must be effectively used in the production activities of the enterprise to maintain its competitiveness. The economic essence

of the intellectual potential of an enterprise is also determined by the emergence of the system of relations of its components and the presence of cause-and-effect relationships between them. Therefore, the next stage of our research will be to determine the structural components of the intellectual potential of an enterprise and identify the presence of cause-and-effect relationships between them.

The structure of an enterprise's intellectual potential can be represented as a set of intangible intellectual resources that it possesses and which can be used to create innovative products and increase the value of the enterprise's assets [7]. As you know, the market value of an enterprise's assets is influenced by all factors of production that form its income. In the context of the development of the knowledge economy, it seems legitimate to assert that the importance of intellectual resources in the formation of the market value of an enterprise's assets becomes a determining factor of production [8].

Currently, the most common approach is that there are three main components of the structure of intellectual potential: intellectual capital (intellectual abilities of enterprise personnel and the possibilities of their effective use), social (managerial) capital and organizational (structural) capital (intellectual technologies, software products and others informational resources). The last two structural components are nothing more than technologies for managing an enterprise and its production activities, as well as relationships with the enterprise's counterparties).

At the same time, management information technologies in modern conditions make it advisable to separate them into a separate – fourth (information) – structural component of the intellectual potential of an enterprise. This proposal can be justified quite easily if we take into account the fact that modern information technologies are formed on the basis of the generation of new knowledge and represent an intellectual resource, partly related to the intellectual property of an enterprise, along with such forms of its manifestation as inventions, utility models, trademarks, industrial brands, know-how, etc. In other words, the information component of the structure of intellectual potential will contribute to its development and growth only in the conditions of regular R&D by the enterprise [9].

To measure the intellectual potential of an enterprise, generally accepted approaches have not yet been developed. At the same time, many researchers adhere to the theory that to assess it is possible to use integral indicators that characterize the development of the intellectual potential of the main divisions, and therefore the entire enterprise. The intellectual potential of an enterprise should be assessed at least once a quarter. This will allow you to constantly monitor the dynamics of its changes and timely make appropriate management decisions and carry out the necessary organizational measures in order to ensure the effective use of the intellectual potential of the enterprise, the development of its production activities and maintaining competitiveness in the domestic and foreign markets. This entails

the need to include another (fifth) component in the structure of the enterprise's intellectual potential - dynamic, which allows one to track possible changes in the assessments of its measurement over time and, on this basis, quickly make management decisions to maintain a certain value of the calculated indicators.

Based on the results of the study, the structural composition of the intellectual potential of the enterprise, in addition to three traditional components - intellectual capital (intellectual abilities of the enterprise personnel and the possibility of their effective use), social (managerial) capital and organizational (structural) capital (intellectual technologies, software products and other information resources) - was supplemented with two fundamentally new components - informational and dynamic, which make it possible to take into account to the maximum extent its influence on increasing the competitiveness of domestic enterprises in modern economic conditions. Thus, the approach proposed by the authors to defining the concept of intellectual potential and its structural components has signs of novelty. At the same time, the authors do not claim to be completely complete either in the very definition of the concept of intellectual potential or in determining the essence of its traditional and proposed new structural components. Currently, these issues have not been sufficiently studied in modern economic science, despite the presence of a fairly large number of existing and newly emerging studies. This circumstance even more clearly confirms the relevance and significance of conducting this kind of research in relation to the objective realities of the development of the Russian economy.

Conclusion.

The results obtained allowed us to formulate the following conclusions.

1. In modern conditions, the basis for ensuring sustainable socio-economic development of each country is maintaining the competitiveness of the national economy, which is largely determined by the ability of business structures to generate new knowledge, its effective use and dissemination, as well as the creation of breakthrough information technologies and their application in the production of innovative products.

2. The introduction of modern information technologies in all areas of production and other types of economic activity has contributed to a fundamental change in the nature of human work, which is becoming more and more intellectual.

3. In the conditions of widespread computerization of production, enterprise personnel can be considered as specialists in intellectual work who possess not only new knowledge and information. In other words, knowledge workers become not only one of the defining resources of the knowledge-based information economy, but also form the intellectual potential of modern enterprises.

4. A brief analysis of the most common approaches to defining the concept of intellectual potential of a number of the founders of this theory, as well as domes-

tic researchers who, in their works, developed some approaches in relation to the realities of the Russian economy, is presented.

5. The formulation of the concept of intellectual potential has been clarified, which is most consistent with modern approaches to organizing production, using the knowledge and competencies of personnel, and also includes the conditions necessary to maintain the competitiveness of enterprises.

6. The novelty of the results obtained lies in the expansion of the number of structural components of the intellectual potential of an enterprise from three traditional to five by including two fundamentally new components that make it possible to take into account its influence on increasing the competitiveness of domestic enterprises in modern economic conditions.

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